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PARENTS' PERCEPTION OF OVERSCHOOLING AT THE PRE/PRIMARY EDUCATION LEVEL

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Abstract

This study examined the opinion of parents about overschooling. The study specifically examined parents opinion about length of time children spent in school, amount of homework, amount of school involvement at children's' age and effect of overschooling on children and parents. A sample of 200 parents responded to a 25 item 4-point Likert scale questionnaire. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The result of the study shows that parents were of the opinion that the length of time children spent in school was much, the amount of home work was much, children were overloaded with school activities that did not match their age and the overschooling affects both the children, parents and overall family live. Based on the findings recommendations were made among which is that all stakeholders in education should be made to realize that children need to have time for fun and also develop their interest.

Introduction and Background

Recently, the role of education as an instrument in promoting many desirable goals has increasingly been emphasized. Education is seen as the self-evident vehicle in promoting individual development, national economic growth and a more equitable means of distributing income. These benefits have led to an impressive expansion of schooling and school activities. Enrollments have extended to include children from one and a half years.

In the early years of introduction of formal education by the missionaries, children were enrolled in school at the age of 5 or 6 when they were considered mature enough to be able to cope with the rigors associated with

school learning. Children at this age, were expected to have been matured enough to walk to school alone and return unaccompanied thereby reducing the stress on both the teachers and the parents. Today, such practice has been eroded, children now start school at a very tender age of two or less, are made to study things beyond their age and sit for a very long period of the day without a recreational activities in many cases. This practice of overburdening children by the weight of their excessive schooling is what is considered in this study as overschooling.

Overschooling has been defined variously. Muysken (1998) defines it as many persons working on jobs that require less schooling than obtained. According to Meer (2000)

overschooling has to do with periods of depression when jobs shrink in the labour market and people just avail themselves of what kinds of jobs are available. It is also seen as the extent to which an individual possesses a level of education in excess of that which is required for their particular job (McGuinness, 2006). For this paper, overschooling is seen as the phenomenon in which an individual feels burdened or oppressed by the weight of their schooling. Parents and the education policy makers do not seem to bother if this phenomenon of overschooling is of any benefit to the child in the later life achievements in terms of academic achievement and labour acquisition.

Holts (2005) posits that too much schooling works against education. Educators too often overlook the fact that children learn more outside the classroom than in the classroom. As a result of the society's relentless focus on education or rather exam results, the average child in Nigeria and the world over attends not only regular school, but also a series of after school and holiday lessons that are run privately where they cram English, Mathematics and other core subjects into their already tired heads. Almost 80% of children in Nigeria are forced to attend such lessons either in the school premises or at home despite the normal school hours of 8.00am to 2.00pm.

When western education was introduced to our nation, the kindergarten was a lot of fun. The children learned letters and some basic letter sounds, numbers and children mostly learned how to go to school. The children were taught how to listen to the teacher and how to socialize

with peers. Now the kindergarten class, though still full of fun, is a lot of work. For some children, it is just not fun anymore. By 7 years, our children have graduated from the pre-kindergarten, kindergarten and are already in their primary three or four in most cases. In this attempt to compete with others, we forget to let our children to be children. These children at very tender age will have to learn to read. They must do addition, subtraction and off course doing it mentally by memory and not by reasoning. As much as it is interesting to watch the little children do this, it would not have been less interesting to watch them do the same thing if they were learning the same and more meaningfully a couple of years later. A lot of what the children do in the early days of education seem to be a repetition from one class to another except from grade three where the child's age can be put at about 7 or 8 years.

It is extremely disturbing that so many people feel that their children can learn only if they are over educated. Larocco (2003) noted that creativity is not created in a vacuum, as such, children must have time to play and use their imaginations. Also, most secondary and higher schools look out for well rounded individuals and not automatons. They want children who are socially adept and have varied interests, but this cannot be possible if the children are overbooked. In order for children to become successful adults, they need to learn how to socialize, how to share, how to communicate with others otherwise, they will have a difficult time as adults, especially in the working world. School was not supposed to be 100 percent of a child's life.

Another aspect of overschooling phenomenon considered in this study is the amount of homework assigned to the pupils. Many controversies have been going on concerning the amount of homework given to pupils. According to Gill (2011), the proponents of homework believe that homework is a beneficial practice which is also positively associated with students learning. The reasons given are that (1) it extends the work in the classroom with additional time on task, (2) it develops habits of independent study, (3) it's a form of communication between the school and the parents and (4) gives parents idea of what their children are doing in school. On the other hand, others believe that homework is causing a lot of problems such as nervous breakdown, robbing children of childhood, turning children off learning, destroying family life and stressing up parents to sit up and help with homework (Cooper, 2001 and Hofferth & Sandberg, 2000).

So many people feel that children can learn only if they are overburdened with a lot of homework. Teachers out of concern for children's ability to perform well in entrance examinations tend to overburden children with a lot of homework. On daily basis, pupils are made to stay in school till 4.00pm and still go home with much homework to be submitted the following day. Studies according to McEntire (2006) indicate that teachers in the lower grades assign homework to help children develop time management skills and to review class material. In analyzing more than 100 studies, the researcher reported that in the lower grades, the effect of homework on achievement is minimal, and that too much homework can be

detrimental to family life and pupil's achievement. However, frequency of homework completion does predict the students' grades and may have an impact on later achievement. Chaika (2000) in McEntire (2006) posits that for children from kindergarten to grade 2, homework is most effective when it does not exceed 10 to 20 minutes each day while children in grades three to six can handle 30 to 60 minutes work a day.

Unfortunately, many times this is not the case. Many children take home an average of two or more hours of homework that must be completed for the next day. Claude Golden, a Professor of teacher education at California State University, Long Beach stated that research clearly shows that homework is one of the many things that can help children achieve academically, but that like any good thing, it can be overused and abused (Lambert, 2003). Once a child is engaged beyond 10 hours a week in homework, the benefits seem to level off. Either the children are burnt out or teachers do not assign things worth the extra time.

Also Kralovec in Lambert (2003) narrating the ills of excessive homework, opined that homework is a primary cause of the anxiety and depression children feel. She further suggests that there may be strong links between homework volume and the rise in childhood obesity. Tendre, Baker and Akiba (2005) analyzing data from the 3rd International Study of Mathematics and sciences (TIMSS) collected in 1994 from schools in 4 nations across the 4th, 8th and 12th grades indicated frequent lack of positive correlation between average amount of homework assigned in a

nation and corresponding level of academic achievement.

Researches have shown that overschooling at too early in life may be detrimental not only to a child's development and academic success but contribute to other family challenges. Effects of overschooling include depriving children of play time, reducing family relationship such as time to relax, talk, read, play games and family outings, as well as missing activities that promote self awareness such as children having time on their own to think, dream, draw, create, fantasize and explore special interest (Elkins, 2003; Griffith, 2011 and Tugend, 2011). Over involvement of children in only school related activities is a major encroachment on the amount of time families spend together. Although benefits of such activities have been supported by research, too much of a good thing can tamper with the wellness of the family life. Psychologist blames this culture for all manner of ills from immoral practices unacceptable to the society to the disobedience and stubbornness found in children in primary school age. (Hotdogfish, 2011).

Many children as a result of being over involved in only school related activities lose out on the simple pleasure of play. Playing is children's job and an important one. The United Nations High Commission for Human right recognizes play as a right of every child. Play helps with brain development, personal growth and discovery. However, even occasional boredom can be a good thing. It gives the child the opportunity to daydream, imagine and create (Griffith, 2011). Griffith also pointed out that children

who are involved in extracurricular activities have been shown to have more self confidence, good academic performance and fewer behavioural problems than those who do not. They are said to be likely involved in taking drugs or engage in other risky behaviours.

Statement of the Problem

One of the neglected areas of research has been on the perception of parents about over schooling. This study attempted to redress this by investigating parents' perception of the amount of school based activities of their children.

Objective

The main objective of this study was to investigate parents' perception of overschooling in private nursery and primary schools.

Research Questions

- (1) What is the perception of parents' about length of time children spend in school?
- (2) What is the parents' opinion about the amount of homework given to children?
- (3) What is the perception of parents in regard to the amount of school involvement of children at their age?
- (4) What are parents' views about the effect of overschooling on the children and the family?

Methodology

Design

Due to lack of information and little available researches about parents perception of overschooling, a

phenomenological approach was taken for this study (Broadhurst, 1999). According to Kvale (1996) cited in Broadhurst (1999), phenomenological research attempt to characterize how aspect of the world are perceived by people. This approach was therefore adopted to gain insight into what parents feel about the amount of school work their children are involved, and whether this may have any effect on their lives and that of the family.

Population

The population for this study comprised all parents of pupils attending private nursery/primary schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Sample/Sampling Technique

A convenience sample of parents/guardians of children attending ten (10) private nursery/primary schools in Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State constituted the sample for the study; twenty parents were selected from each school making a total of 200 parents as sample for the study.

Instruments

In conformity with the phenomenological approach, a semi-structured interview with 5 (five) parents and a series of discussions provided the initial framework for the study. All interviews were audio taped and transcribed which was later used in preparing a structured questionnaire that was administered on the selected sample. The interviews were conducted in the home of the participants, where the world of the participants and their views was of importance. The semi-structured interviews allowed flexibility for the questions to be adapted when

necessary. As there was little or no available research on the topic it was necessary to allow scope to pursue the topic. The information collected during the interview session formed the basis for preparing the questionnaire used in this study.

The questionnaire consisted of 25 questions divided into two parts. Part one consisted of 5 questions providing demographic data such as gender, age, marital status, educational level and occupational status. Part two of the questionnaire consisted of twenty items that dealt with the parents level of agreement or disagreement about their perception of overschooling on a 4 point Likert scale of strongly agree (4) to strongly disagree (1).

Procedure

With the help of some research assistants, the researchers visited the schools selected for this study. Permission was sought from each parent with whom the researchers came in contact with. Thereafter, the questionnaire was given out to them. For the parents who were able to complete the questionnaire, the researchers explained the issue involved and there were then asked to complete them. For others, the researchers help in reading out the items which was recorded immediately. Each questionnaire completion lasted approximately 15 to 30 minutes and sometimes a group of parents were approached, interviewed and the recording done concurrently. All subjects were thanked for their patients and willingness to participate in the study.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Frequencies, percentages,

means and standard deviations were used to analyze the data for answering each of the research questions.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the perception of parents' about length of time children spend in school?

Table 1 revealed that the respondents were in agreement with four of the items that relate to the time children spend in school. The mean values of the four items ranged from 3.42 to 3.08. Deduction from the analysis is that parents agree that children spend too long a time in school.

Table 1: Responses on the Length of time children spend in school.

N	STATEMENTS	SD		D		A		SD		X	SD
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1	Most of what is done in lesson after school is not necessary	94	48	88	44	12	6	4	2	3.38*	0.69
2	Keeping children too long in school creates opportunity for interaction with friends and classmates.	24	12	80	40	66	33	30	15	2.49	0.89
3	The change in a child's life is not commensurate with the amount of time they are made to spend in school.	80	40	64	32	48	24	8	4	3.08*	0.89
4	Children are kept longer in school not necessarily for learning but to help parents who may not have help at home.	100	50	88	44	8	4	2	42	3.42*	0.69
5	The extra hours children spend in school are worth it if they must develop properly.	2	1	32	16	90	45	74	38	3.20*	0.74

*= Accepted

Research Question 2

What is the parents' opinion about the amount of homework given to children?

The result shown in table 2 indicated that parents perceive generally that the amount of homework given to the children is too much. The analysis showed mean values above 2.50 cut off point, with the least mean being 3.04.

Table 2: Parents' responses on amount of homework given to children.

N	STATEMENTS	SD		D		A		SD		X	SD
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1	Homework develops in children habit of independent study.	82	41	102	51	14	7	2	1	3.32*	0.64
2	Children do not need too much homework to succeed.	66	33	84	42	42	21	8	4	3.04*	0.84
3	Most homework's are often too	80	40	64	32	48	24	8	4	3.08*	0.89

	demanding for children's age.	82	41	90	45	24	12	4	2	3.25*	0.7
4	Children get so tired after the long stay in school that doing homework becomes a burden.										
5	To reduce childrens homework is to create room for idleness.	108	54	70	35	22	11	-	-	3.24*	0.65

school involvement of children at their age? The result for this is shown in table 3.

Research Question 3

What is the perception of parents in regard to the amount of

Table 3: Parents responses on School involvement of children at their age.

N	STATEMENTS	SD		D		A		SD		X	S
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1	Children start school at too early an age.	-	-	72	36	90	45	38	19	2.17	0.7
2	Most children start school too early because of lack of house help.	92	46	18	9	16	8	74	37	2.64*	0.3
3	The instruction given to children are just enough for their age.	58	29	48	24	62	31	32	16	2.66*	1.0
4	Most time, the school work given to the children is too high for their age.	84	42	80	40	36	10	-	-	3.24*	0.7
5	I do not bother whether or not my child is taught things that are higher than his age.	38	19	22	11	60	30	80	40	2.67*	0.9

The finding in table 3 revealed that parents perception of overschooling in terms of volume of school work given to the children at their age was too high with a mean value of 3.24. The perception of parents about children starting school at too early an age had a mean value of 2.17. This indicates that parents do not believe the age their children enter school is too early.

Research Question 4

What are parents views about the effect of overschooling on the children and the family?

Table 4 reveals that the mean score of all the items was above 2.50 cut off point except for one item. This implies that the parents are of the opinion that overschooling has an effect on both the children and the entire family.

Table 4: Parents responses on the effects of overschooling

N	STATEMENTS	SD		D		A		SD		X	S
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1	Too much engagement in school activities contribute to childrens rebellious behaviour.	10	5	30	15	70	35	90	45	2.38	0.6
2	Due to too much school work, the	84	42	66	33	36	18	12	6	2.73*	0.6

children have no time for leisure.

Too much school work does not leave anytime for family life.	48	24	66	33	60	30	26	13	2.68*	0.98
The schools are putting too much stress on our young children.	82	41	38	19	52	26	28	14	2.65*	0.94
Much activity in the school robs the children of childhood fun.	58	29	62	31	48	24	32	16	2.66*	1.04

Discussion

Parents perception about length of time children spend in school was generally accepted to be too long. They did not accept that the extra time spent in school will create opportunity for their interaction with friends and class mates. This is so because many times even the teachers are tired after spending the first four hours with the children. Having to spend another two hours just amount to a waste of the childs leisure hours since the teacher and the children are already too tired to be effective. This is in line with Laroccos (1999) assertion that getting children overschooled does not give them an opportunity to socialize, to share and to communicate with others, which eventually creates problems in their adults life.

School was not supposed to be 100% of a childs life (Larocco, 1999). Its time we help our children by really examining what is important and understanding that our goal should be to create healthy, happy and sane adults. Overschooling does not guarantee that. Psychologists blame this culture of excessive retention of children in school for all manner of social ills, from immoral practices unacceptable to the society to the disobedience and stubbornness found in children at the primary school age. (Hotdogfish, 2011). An explanation may be that, most working class parents feel that the children are more secure in the hands of the school

teachers than being left alone at home, so they tend to take advantage of that and simply dump their young children at school by 7.30a.m only to reappear by the close of their days work by 4 or 5p.m.

Concerning the amount of homework given to children, all parents sampled accepted that homework is good in that it is helpful in developing childrens habit for independent study and also reduces the idle moments that children would have been involved in undesirable activities. This is in agreement with the proponents of home work, Grill (2011) who believes that homework is positively associated with childrens learning. McEntire (2006) portraying the benefits of homework indicates that teachers in the lower grade assign homework to help children develop time management skill and ability to review class materials. However, parents feel that children get too tired after the long school day to be given another burdening set of work to go home with. This opinion is shared by Cooper, (2011); Lambert, Hoffath & Sandberg, (2000) and Lambert (2003); Lambert asserts that once a child is engaged beyond 10 hours a week, the benefit seems to level off; either the children are burnt out or teachers did not assign things worth the extra time.

child is assigned 50 past questions in Quantitative reasoning or mathematics in one day's homework become an abuse to the child and can never help the child to achieve academically.

Too much homework can be counterproductive. Rather than improve educational achievement in countries around the world, increase in home work may actually undercut teaching effectiveness and worsen disparities in students' learning. Teachers assign homework mostly as drill, to improve memorization of material either in mathematics, science or the humanities. While drills and repetitive exercise have place in schooling, homework may not take that place.

Teachers in private schools do not seem to bother about the volume of assignments they give to the children. It seems that the age, mental capacity and even the child's leisure must all be sacrificed in school work. At the end of the day, it is not only the child who is stressed up, but the parents who have to assist the child in doing the homework and of course the family live in many cases is tampered with as a result of day to day business to tackle excessive homework for too or three children. It is needful to reduce the amount of homework given to children and allow them more leisure from the rigors of schooling.

Results presented in table 3 revealed that amount of school work assigned to the children at their age are too much. The above agrees with the view of Lambert (2003) who asserts that too much school work is a primary cause of the anxiety and depression children feel. She further suggests that there may be strong links between

volume of children's work and the rise in childhood obesity. The perfect picture of a balanced childhood is, one in which our children go to school, do a little homework and play around, is a myth for many children. More and more children like adults are involved in too many activities.

Unfortunately, a number of parents are of the opinion that children do not start school at too early an age. Discussion with most parents revealed that these parents do not have help to take care of the children at home and so they have to pursue their career. The only alternative is to carry these children to school for safe keeping and that has led to the proliferation of crèches in the schools. The result of this is that as the children stay up to 1½ years of age in the crèches they are automatically transferred to the formal school environment where they are forced to begin schooling at such a tender age.

Results presented in table 4 showed that the parents' perception of effects of overschooling on the lives of both the child and family can be devastating. From the baseline data, most parents were of the opinion that children no longer have leisure time and childhood fun as they find greater part of their daily lives being overstressed with too much school work. This is in agreement with Garfield (2011) who believes that children should have many outside activities and that they need to live fully as children. To have them work for six hours at school and then go home and work for hours at evening does not seem right as it does not allow them to have a childhood.

Apart from the fact that children need to make out time for fun outside the school, even in the school premises within the confine of the school hours, most schools have no provision for recreation. Any little space the school has is used for expansion after the initial approval by the Ministry of Education. Therefore, children are forced during break time to inconveniently place their heads on the desk in the name of rest, and this adds to children's boredom. As a result of the over involvement, many children have lost out on the simple pleasure of play (Griffith, 2011). Play is children's job and an important one. In fact, the United Nations High Commission for Human rights recognizes play as a right of every child. Play helps with brain development and helps with personal growth and discovery.

In support of this, Osenenko (2011) suggests placing less focus on test scores in the early years of schooling and spending more time on allowing the children learn in the way that comes most natural to them by playing. This would boost all the so important test scores in the later years of children's schooling. If children must attend schools at such an early age, owing in no small part to socio-economic realities in the country, then what and how the young minds are being taught needs closer scrutiny. Young children love to learn and to have fun. Converting that reality into a school's curriculum seems more preferable. Enough emphasis should be given to developing demonstrative social skills, manners and a desire to learn. Teachers should teach with more emphasis on the fun of learning, not just the 3R's, but the arts, manners, respect and other social skill as well. Let the children fail a test and

then teach them how to learn from their failure and how to succeed in the future.

Moreover, over involvement of children in only school related activities is a major encroachment on the amount of time families spend together. Although benefits of such activities have been supported by researches, too much of a good thing can tamper with the wellness of the family life. Stress on both children and parents have apparently increased over time due to over schooling, as children of very tender ages having to stay too long at school and longer into the night studying alone or with parents as the case may be. Griffith (2011) has summed up overall stress effect of over schooling on children as leading to physical symptoms such as headache, thumb sucking, bedwetting, poor grade and behavioural problems. It is advisable, he suggests, reducing the amount of school activities as this will give the child some free time.

Conclusion

The study has established the general view of parents that there is over schooling at the pre/primary education level. This phenomenon of overschooling does adversely affect the development of a child not only academically but socially and psychologically and subsequently impacts negatively on their adult life.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the research findings, the following recommendations are made as a way of encouraging the academic progress of children without over schooling:

- (1) Government should give priority attention to school enrollment, to ensure that children below the age of

four years are not given too much to lean at a time..

(2) Proper monitoring of schools and supervision on regular basis should be made to ensure that recreational facilities are made available in all schools to make children enjoy their childhood.

(3) Government should come in to regulate the activities of the private schools such as making sure that the schools follow the appropriate curriculum for pre and primary education level.

(4) Government should organize seminars for heads of private and public schools to help harmonize school activities by making sure that they have and follow the same calendar, reducing the amount of homework given to children so as to conform with their age level and time spent in school in order to improve family life.

(5) Organizations such as churches, NGOs etc should organize seminars to help parents become aware of the psychological impacts of sending children too early to school thereby denying them early childhood attention.

(6) The proprietors and heads of schools should reduce the amount of homework or school activities that require more of the mental ability and time of the children. They should be given time to develop their personal and social skills.

(7) All stakeholders in education should be made to realize that children need to have time for fun and also develop their interest.

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